

language_metadata

glottocode	name	doculect	macroarea	family
abkh1244	Abkhaz	lexibank-northeastalex-abkhaz	Eurasia	Abkhaz-Adyge
abui1241	Abui	lexibank-robinsonap-abui	Papunesia	Timor-Alor-Pantar
acha1250	Achagua	lexibank-hubercolumbian-achagua	Americas	Arawakan
adan1251	Adang	lexibank-robinsonap-adang	Papunesia	Timor-Alor-Pantar
adny1235	Adnyamathanha	ausphonlex_v0-4:Adnyamathanha	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
adyg1241	Adyghe	lexibank-northeastalex-adyghe	Eurasia	Abkhaz-Adyge
ainu1240	Hokkaidoainu	lexibank-northeastalex-hokkaidoainu	Eurasia	Ainu
alaw1244	Alawa	ausphonlex_v0-4:Alawa	Australia	Mangarrayi-Maran
alba1267	Standardalbanian	lexibank-northeastalex-standardalbanian	Eurasia	Indo-European
aleu1260	Aleut	lexibank-northeastalex-aleut	Americas	Eskimo-Aleut
alor1249	Alorantar	lexibank-robinsonap-alorantar	Papunesia	Timor-Alor-Pantar
amai1246	Amaimon	lexibank-zraggenmadang-amaimon	Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea
amar1271	Amurdak	ausphonlex_v0-4:Amurdak	Australia	IwaidjanProper
amel1241	Amele	lexibank-zraggenmadang-amele	Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea
amii1238	Emmi	ausphonlex_v0-4:Emmi	Australia	WesternDaly
anam1247	Anam	lexibank-zraggenmadang-anam	Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea
anam1248	Anamgura	lexibank-zraggenmadang-anamgura	Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea
angg1238	Angkamuthi	ausphonlex_v0-4:Angkamuthi	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
angu1242	Anguthimri	ausphonlex_v0-4:Anguthimri	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
anja1238	Anjam	lexibank-zraggenmadang-anjam	Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea
apali1256	Apali	lexibank-zraggenmadang-apali	Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea
araw1272	Arawum	lexibank-zraggenmadang-arawum	Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea
arhu1242	Ika	lexibank-hubercolumbian-ika	Americas	Chibchan
asas1240	Asas	lexibank-zraggenmadang-asas	Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea
atam1239	Atampaya	ausphonlex_v0-4:Atampaya	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
atem1241	Atemble	lexibank-zraggenmadang-atemble	Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea
avar1256	Avar	lexibank-northeastalex-avar	Eurasia	Nakh-Daghestanian
awac1239	Awa	lexibank-hubercolumbian-awa	Americas	Barbacoan
ayab1239	Ayapathu	ausphonlex_v0-4:Ayapathu	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
ayab1239	Yintyingka	ausphonlex_v0-4:Yintyingka	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
badi1246	Badimaya	ausphonlex_v0-4:Badimaya	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
bagu1252	Bagupi	lexibank-zraggenmadang-bagupi	Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea
baim1245	Baimak	lexibank-zraggenmadang-baimak	Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea
waal1238	Waalubal	ausphonlex_v0-4:Waalubal	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
bani1254	Baniva	lexibank-hubercolumbian-baniva	Americas	Arawakan
bara1380	Barasana	lexibank-hubercolumbian-barasana	Americas	Tucanoan
bard1255	Bardi	ausphonlex_v0-4:Bardi	Australia	Nyulnyulan
barg1252	Bargam	lexibank-zraggenmadang-bargam	Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea

bari1297	Bari	lexibank-hubercolumbian-bari	Americas	Chibchan
bash1264	Bashkir	lexibank-northeuralex-bashkir	Eurasia	Turkic
basq1248	Basque	lexibank-northeuralex-basque	Eurasia	Basque
basu1242	Epenabasurudo	lexibank-hubercolumbian-epenabasurudo	Americas	Chocoan
basu1242	Epenasaija	lexibank-hubercolumbian-epenasaija	Americas	Chocoan
baty1234	Butchulla	ausphonlex_v0-4:Butchulla	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
bauu1244	Bau	lexibank-zraggenmadang-bau	Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea
bayu1240	Payungu	ausphonlex_v0-4:Payungu	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
beij1234	Beijing	lexibank-beidasinitic-Beijing	Eurasia	Sino-Tibetan
bela1254	Belarusian	lexibank-northeuralex-belarusian	Eurasia	Indo-European
beng1280	Bengali	lexibank-northeuralex-bengali	Eurasia	Indo-European
bepo1240	Bepour	lexibank-zraggenmadang-bepour	Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea
bidy1243	Bidyara	ausphonlex_v0-4:Bidyara	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
bila1257	Bilakura	lexibank-zraggenmadang-bilakura	Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea
bili1250	Bilinarra	ausphonlex_v0-4:Bilinarra	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
biri1256	Biri	ausphonlex_v0-4:Biri	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
biri1256	Wiri	ausphonlex_v0-4:Wiri	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
biyo1244	Biyom	lexibank-zraggenmadang-biyom	Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea
blag1240	Blagar	lexibank-robinsonap-blagar	Papunesia	Timor-Alor-Pantar
bong1291	Bongu	lexibank-zraggenmadang-bongu	Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea
brem1238	Brem	lexibank-zraggenmadang-brem	Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea
bret1244	Breton	lexibank-northeuralex-breton	Eurasia	Indo-European
bula1255	Bularnu	ausphonlex_v0-4:Bularnu	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
bulg1262	Bulgarian	lexibank-northeuralex-bulgarian	Eurasia	Indo-European
buna1275	Bunuba	ausphonlex_v0-4:Bunuba	Australia	Bunaban
bura1267	Burarra	ausphonlex_v0-4:Burarra	Australia	Maningrida
burd1238	Purduna	ausphonlex_v0-4:Purduna	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
huri1258	Buryat	lexibank-northeuralex-buryat	Eurasia	Mongolic-Khitian
buru1296	Burushaski	lexibank-northeuralex-burushaski	Eurasia	Burushaski
cabi1241	Cabiyari	lexibank-hubercolumbian-cabiyari	Americas	Arawakan
cacu1241	Kakua	lexibank-hubercolumbian-kakua	Americas	Kakua-Nukak
cams1241	Kamsa	lexibank-hubercolumbian-kamsa	Americas	Camsá
cara1272	Carapana	lexibank-hubercolumbian-carapana	Americas	Tucanoan
cari1279	Carijona	lexibank-hubercolumbian-carijona	Americas	Cariban
cent2128	Centralsiberianyupik	lexibank-northeuralex-centralsiberianyupik	Eurasia	Eskimo-Aleut
cent2150	Tunebocentral	lexibank-hubercolumbian-tunebocentral	Americas	Chibchan
chac1249	Chapalaachi	lexibank-hubercolumbian-chapalaachi	Americas	Barbacoan
chan1326	Changsha	lexibank-beidasinitic-Changsha	Eurasia	Sino-Tibetan
chao1238	Chaozhou	lexibank-beidasinitic-Chaozhou	Eurasia	Sino-Tibetan
chec1245	Chechen	lexibank-northeuralex-chechen	Eurasia	Nakh-Daghestanian

chen1267	Chengdu	lexibank-beidasinitic-Chengdu	Eurasia	Sino-Tibetan
chim1309	Chimila	lexibank-hubercolumbian-chimila	Americas	Chibchan
chuk1273	Chukchi	lexibank-northeuralex-chukchi	Eurasia	Chukotko-Kamchatkan
chuv1255	Chuvash	lexibank-northeuralex-chuvash	Eurasia	Turkic
cogu1240	Kogui	lexibank-hubercolumbian-kogui	Americas	Chibchan
colo1256	Tsafiquipila	lexibank-hubercolumbian-tsafiquipila	Americas	Barbacoan
croa1245	Croatian	lexibank-northeuralex-croatian	Eurasia	Indo-European
cube1242	Cubeo	lexibank-hubercolumbian-cubeo	Americas	Tucanoan
cuib1242	Cuiba	lexibank-hubercolumbian-cuiba	Americas	Guahiboan
curr1243	Curripaco	lexibank-hubercolumbian-curripaco	Americas	Arawakan
czec1258	Czech	lexibank-northeuralex-czech	Eurasia	Indo-European
dana1254	Danaru	lexibank-zraggenmadang-danaru	Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea
dani1285	Danish	lexibank-northeuralex-danish	Eurasia	Indo-European
darg1241	Dargwa	lexibank-northeuralex-dargwa	Eurasia	Nakh-Daghestanian
dar11243	Southern Paakinty	ausphonlex_v0-4:Southern Paakintyi	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
desa1247	Desano	lexibank-hubercolumbian-desano	Americas	Tucanoan
dhal1245	Thalanyji	ausphonlex_v0-4:Thalanyji	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
dhal1246	Dhay'yi	ausphonlex_v0-4:Dhay'yi	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
dhan1270	Dhangu	ausphonlex_v0-4:Dhangu	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
dhar1247	Tharrkari	ausphonlex_v0-4:Tharrkari	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
dhar1248	Dharumbal	ausphonlex_v0-4:Dharumbal	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
dido1241	Tsez	lexibank-northeuralex-tsez	Eurasia	Nakh-Daghestanian
diye1234	Diyari	ausphonlex_v0-4:Diyari	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
dimi1244	Gavak	lexibank-zraggenmadang-gavak	Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea
dira1238	Thirarri	ausphonlex_v0-4:Thirarri	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
djap1238	Djapu	ausphonlex_v0-4:Djapu	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
djau1244	Jawoyn	ausphonlex_v0-4:Jawoyn	Australia	Gunwinyguan
djin1253	Djinang	ausphonlex_v0-4:Djinang	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
djiw1241	Jiwarli	ausphonlex_v0-4:Jiwarli	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
dudu1240	Uyajitaya	lexibank-zraggenmadang-uyajitaya	Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea
dump1243	Watiwa	lexibank-zraggenmadang-watiwa	Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea
dutc1256	Dutch	lexibank-northeuralex-dutch	Eurasia	Indo-European
duun1241	Duungidjawan	ausphonlex_v0-4:Duungidjawan	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
dyaa1242	Djabugay	ausphonlex_v0-4:Djabugay	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
dyir1250	Dyirbal	ausphonlex_v0-4:Dyirbal	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
east2328	Meadowmari	lexibank-northeuralex-meadowmari	Eurasia	Uralic
east2380	Eastern Anmatyerre	ausphonlex_v0-4:Eastern Anmatyerre	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
east2560	Waimaja	lexibank-hubercolumbian-waimaja	Americas	Tucanoan
embe1260	Catio	lexibank-hubercolumbian-catio	Americas	Chocoan
embe1261	Emberatado	lexibank-hubercolumbian-emberatado	Americas	Chocoan

embe1262	Emberachami	lexibank-hubercolumbian-emberachami	Americas	Chocoan
erre1238	Erre	ausphonlex_v0-4:Erre	Australia	Giimbiyu
eryu1239	Eryuan	lexibank-allenbai-Eryuan	Eurasia	Sino-Tibetan
erzy1239	Erzya	lexibank-northeuralex-erzya	Eurasia	Uralic
esto1258	Estonian	lexibank-northeuralex-estonian	Eurasia	Uralic
even1259	Evenki	lexibank-northeuralex-evenki	Eurasia	Tungusic
fait1240	Faita	lexibank-zraggenmadang-faita	Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea
finn1318	Finnish	lexibank-northeuralex-finnish	Eurasia	Uralic
fore1265	Forestenets	lexibank-northeuralex-forestenets	Eurasia	Uralic
fuzh1239	Fuzhou	lexibank-beidasinitic-Fuzhou	Eurasia	Sino-Tibetan
gall1278	Gal	lexibank-zraggenmadang-gal	Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea
gami1243	Gamilaraay	ausphonlex_v0-4:Gamilaraay	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
gang1268	Gangulu	ausphonlex_v0-4:Gangulu	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
gang1270	Ganglau	lexibank-zraggenmadang-ganglau	Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea
garu1246	Garus	lexibank-zraggenmadang-garus	Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea
gida1240	Gidabal	ausphonlex_v0-4:Gidabal	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
gily1242	Nivkh	lexibank-northeuralex-nivkh	Eurasia	Nivkh
gira1247	Girawa	lexibank-zraggenmadang-girawa	Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea
goon1238	Gooniyandi	ausphonlex_v0-4:Gooniyandi	Australia	Bunaban
guah1255	Guahibo	lexibank-hubercolumbian-guahibo	Americas	Guahiboan
guam1248	Guambiano	lexibank-hubercolumbian-guambiano	Americas	Barbacoan
guan1269	Wanano	lexibank-hubercolumbian-wanano	Americas	Tucanoan
guan1279	Guangzhou	lexibank-beidasinitic-Guangzhou	Eurasia	Sino-Tibetan
guay1257	Guayabero	lexibank-hubercolumbian-guayabero	Americas	Guahiboan
guda1243	Gudanji	ausphonlex_v0-4:Gudanji	Australia	Mirndi
gugu1253	Gugu Badhun	ausphonlex_v0-4:Gugu Badhun	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
gugu1254	Koko Bera	ausphonlex_v0-4:Koko Bera	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
gugu1255	Guugu Yimidhirr	ausphonlex_v0-4:Guugu Yimidhirr	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
guma1255	Gumalu	lexibank-zraggenmadang-gumalu	Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea
gund1246	Gun-Djeihmi	ausphonlex_v0-4:Gun-Djeihmi	Australia	Gunwinyguan
guma1252	Kunwinjku	ausphonlex_v0-4:Kunwinjku	Australia	Gunwinyguan
guny1241	Gunya	ausphonlex_v0-4:Gunya	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
gupa1247	Gupapuyngu	ausphonlex_v0-4:Gupapuyngu	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
gura1252	Gurr-Goni	ausphonlex_v0-4:Gurr-Goni	Australia	Maningrida
gurd1238	Kurtjar	ausphonlex_v0-4:Kurtjar	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
guri1247	Gurindji	ausphonlex_v0-4:Gurindji	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
guwa1243	Guwamu	ausphonlex_v0-4:Guwamu	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
halh1238	Khalkhamongolian	lexibank-northeuralex-khalkhamongolian	Eurasia	Mongolic-Khitan
hebr1245	Modernhebrew	lexibank-northeuralex-modernhebrew	Eurasia	Afro-Asiatic
hefe1234	Hefei	lexibank-beidasinitic-Hefei	Eurasia	Sino-Tibetan

heqi1238	Heqing	lexibank-allenbai-Heqing	Eurasia	Sino-Tibetan
hind1269	Hindi	lexibank-northeuralex-hindi	Eurasia	Indo-European
hung1274	Hungarian	lexibank-northeuralex-hungarian	Eurasia	Uralic
hupd1244	Jupda	lexibank-hubercolumbian-jupda	Americas	Naduhup
icel1247	Icelandic	lexibank-northeuralex-icelandic	Eurasia	Indo-European
ikar1243	Ikarranggal	ausphonlex_v0-4:Ikarranggal	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
ikar1243	Ogh Angkula	ausphonlex_v0-4:Ogh Angkula	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
inar1241	Inarisami	lexibank-northeuralex-inarisami	Eurasia	Uralic
inga1252	Inga	lexibank-hubercolumbian-inga	Americas	Quechuan
iris1253	Irish	lexibank-northeuralex-irish	Eurasia	Indo-European
isab1240	Isabi	lexibank-zraggenmadang-isabi	Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea
iseb1246	Isebe	lexibank-zraggenmadang-isebe	Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea
ital1282	Italian	lexibank-northeuralex-italian	Eurasia	Indo-European
itel1242	Itelmen	lexibank-northeuralex-itelmen	Eurasia	Chukotko-Kamchatkan
iwai1244	Iwaidja	ausphonlex_v0-4:Iwaidja	Australia	IwaidjanProper
jaru1254	Jaru	ausphonlex_v0-4:Jaru	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
jian1239	Jianchuan	lexibank-allenbai-Jianchuan	Eurasia	Sino-Tibetan
jili1241	Jilim	lexibank-zraggenmadang-jilim	Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea
jina1245	Jinan	lexibank-beidasinitic-Jinan	Eurasia	Sino-Tibetan
kaer1234	Kaera	lexibank-robinsonap-kaera	Papunesia	Timor-Alor-Pantar
kala1399	Kalaallisut	lexibank-northeuralex-kalaallisut	Americas	Eskimo-Aleut
kalk1246	Kalkatungu	ausphonlex_v0-4:Kalkatungu	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
kalm1243	Kalmyk	lexibank-northeuralex-kalmyk	Eurasia	Mongolic-Khitian
kama1365	Kamang	lexibank-robinsonap-kamang	Papunesia	Timor-Alor-Pantar
kanj1260	Kaantju	ausphonlex_v0-4:Kaantju	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
kara1476	Karajarri	ausphonlex_v0-4:Karajarri	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
kare1335	Northkarelian	lexibank-northeuralex-northkarelian	Eurasia	Uralic
kare1341	Kare	lexibank-zraggenmadang-kare	Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea
kari1304	Kariyarra	ausphonlex_v0-4:Kariyarra	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
kart1247	Kartujarra	ausphonlex_v0-4:Kartujarra	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
kawa1290	Ogh Unyjan	ausphonlex_v0-4:Ogh Unyjan	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
kaza1248	Kazakh	lexibank-northeuralex-kazakh	Eurasia	Turkic
kein1239	Kein	lexibank-zraggenmadang-kein	Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea
kelo1247	Klon	lexibank-robinsonap-klon	Papunesia	Timor-Alor-Pantar
kesa1244	Kesawai	lexibank-zraggenmadang-kesawai	Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea
kett1243	Ket	lexibank-northeuralex-ket	Eurasia	Yeniseian
khan1273	Northernkhanty	lexibank-northeuralex-northernkhanty	Eurasia	Uralic
kild1236	Kildinsami	lexibank-northeuralex-kildinsami	Eurasia	Uralic
kitj1240	Kija	ausphonlex_v0-4:Kija	Australia	Jarrakan
kobo1248	Kobol	lexibank-zraggenmadang-kobol	Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea

kokn1236	Kok Nar	ausphonlex_v0-4:Kok Nar	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
kolo1267	Migum	lexibank-zraggenmadang-migum	Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea
komi1268	Komizyrian	lexibank-northeuralex-komizyrian	Eurasia	Uralic
komi1269	Komipermyak	lexibank-northeuralex-komipermyak	Eurasia	Uralic
kora1296	Korak	lexibank-zraggenmadang-korak	Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea
kore1280	Korean	lexibank-northeuralex-korean	Eurasia	Koreanic
kore1283	Koreguaje	lexibank-hubercolumbian-koreguaje	Americas	Tucanoan
kowa1245	Kowaki	lexibank-zraggenmadang-kowaki	Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea
kuii1254	Kui	lexibank-robinsonap-kui	Papunesia	Timor-Alor-Pantar
kuka1246	Kukatja	ausphonlex_v0-4:Kukatja	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
kuku1273	Kuku Yalanji	ausphonlex_v0-4:Kuku Yalanji	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
kumb1268	Gumbaynggir	ausphonlex_v0-4:Gumbaynggir	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
kung1258	Gunggari	ausphonlex_v0-4:Gunggari	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
kunm1234	Kunming	lexibank-beidasinitic-Kunming	Eurasia	Sino-Tibetan
kurr1243	Kurrama	ausphonlex_v0-4:Kurrama	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
kuuk1238	Kuugu Ya'u	ausphonlex_v0-4:Kuugu Ya'u	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
kuun1236	Kungkari	ausphonlex_v0-4:Kungkari	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
kwat1244	Waube	lexibank-zraggenmadang-waube	Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea
lakk1252	Lak	lexibank-northeuralex-lak	Eurasia	Nakh-Daghestanian
lamm1241	Westernpantar	lexibank-robinsonap-westernpantar	Papunesia	Timor-Alor-Pantar
lanp1241	Lanping	lexibank-allenbai-Lanping	Eurasia	Sino-Tibetan
lara1258	Larrakia	ausphonlex_v0-4:Larrakia	Australia	Laragia
lard1243	Lardil	ausphonlex_v0-4:Lardil	Australia	Tangkic
lati1261	Latin	lexibank-northeuralex-latin	Eurasia	Indo-European
latv1249	Latvian	lexibank-northeuralex-latvian	Eurasia	Indo-European
lemi1243	Lemio	lexibank-zraggenmadang-lemio	Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea
leni1238	Linngithigh	ausphonlex_v0-4:Linngithigh	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
lezg1247	Lezgian	lexibank-northeuralex-lezgian	Eurasia	Nakh-Daghestanian
limi1242	Limilngan	ausphonlex_v0-4:Limilngan	Australia	Limilngan-Wulna
lith1251	Lithuanian	lexibank-northeuralex-lithuanian	Eurasia	Indo-European
livv1243	Olonetskarelian	lexibank-northeuralex-olonetskarelian	Eurasia	Uralic
livv1244	Livonian	lexibank-northeuralex-livonian	Eurasia	Uralic
lule1254	Lulesami	lexibank-northeuralex-lulesami	Eurasia	Uralic
maca1259	Jitnu	lexibank-hubercolumbian-jitnu	Americas	Guahiboan
macu1260	Macuna	lexibank-hubercolumbian-macuna	Americas	Tucanoan
madn1237	Matngele	ausphonlex_v0-4:Matngele	Australia	EasternDaly
mala1464	Malayalam	lexibank-northeuralex-malayalam	Eurasia	Dravidian
mala1494	Mala	lexibank-zraggenmadang-mala	Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea
mala1495	Malas	lexibank-zraggenmadang-malas	Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea
mala1522	Dimina	lexibank-hubercolumbian-dimina	Americas	Chibchan

male1291	Male	lexibank-zraggenmadang-male	Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea
malg1242	Malkana	ausphonlex_v0-4:Malkana	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
maln1239	Malngin	ausphonlex_v0-4:Malngin	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
maly1234	Malyangapa	ausphonlex_v0-4:Malyangapa	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
manc1252	Manchu	lexibank-northeuralex-manchu	Eurasia	Tungusic
mand1415	Mandarinchinese	lexibank-northeuralex-mandarinchinese	Eurasia	Sino-Tibetan
mang1381	Mangarrayi	ausphonlex_v0-4:Mangarrayi	Australia	Mangarrayi-Maran
mang1382	Mengerrdji	ausphonlex_v0-4:Mengerrdji	Australia	Giimbiyu
mang1383	Mangala	ausphonlex_v0-4:Mangala	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
mans1258	Northernmansi	lexibank-northeuralex-northernmansi	Eurasia	Uralic
mara1385	Marra	ausphonlex_v0-4:Marra	Australia	Mangarrayi-Maran
marg1253	Margany	ausphonlex_v0-4:Margany	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
mart1255	Martuthunira	ausphonlex_v0-4:Martuthunira	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
mate1260	Matepi	lexibank-zraggenmadang-matepi	Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea
maun1240	Mawng	ausphonlex_v0-4:Mawng	Australia	IwaidjanProper
mauw1238	Mauwake	lexibank-zraggenmadang-mauwake	Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea
mawa1266	Mawak	lexibank-zraggenmadang-mawak	Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea
mawa1267	Mawan	lexibank-zraggenmadang-mawan	Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea
mbab1239	Mbabaram	ausphonlex_v0-4:Mbabaram	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
mbar1253	Rimanggudinhma	ausphonlex_v0-4:Rimanggudinhma	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
mian1254	Miani	lexibank-zraggenmadang-miani	Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea
mini1256	Witotominica	lexibank-hubercolumbian-witotominica	Americas	Huitotoan
mira1254	Mirana	lexibank-hubercolumbian-mirana	Americas	Boran
miri1266	Miriwoong	ausphonlex_v0-4:Miriwoong	Australia	Jarrakan
kala1379	Mirriny	ausphonlex_v0-4:Mirriny	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
mode1248	Moderngreek	lexibank-northeuralex-moderngreek	Eurasia	Indo-European
moer1240	Moere	lexibank-zraggenmadang-moere	Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea
moks1248	Moksha	lexibank-northeuralex-moksha	Eurasia	Uralic
more1258	Moresada	lexibank-zraggenmadang-moresada	Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea
mosi1248	Mosimo	lexibank-zraggenmadang-mosimo	Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea
mpar1238	Central Arrernte	ausphonlex_v0-4:Central Arrernte	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
mudb1240	Mudburra	ausphonlex_v0-4:Mudburra	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
muin1242	Muinane	lexibank-hubercolumbian-muinane	Americas	Boran
mumm1238	Mum	lexibank-zraggenmadang-mum	Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea
muni1257	Munit	lexibank-zraggenmadang-munit	Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea
mura1269	Kuninjku	ausphonlex_v0-4:Kuninjku	Australia	Gunwinyguan
murr1258	Murrinh-Patha	ausphonlex_v0-4:Murrinh-patha	Australia	SouthernDaly
mur1266	Muruwari	ausphonlex_v0-4:Muruwari	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
mur1273	Murupi	lexibank-zraggenmadang-murupi	Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea
mur1274	Witotomurui	lexibank-hubercolumbian-witotomurui	Americas	Huitotoan

musa1265	Musar	lexibank-zraggenmadang-musar	Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea
musa1266	Musak	lexibank-zraggenmadang-musak	Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea
naka1260	Nakara	ausphonlex_v0-4:Nakara	Australia	Maningrida
nake1240	Nake	lexibank-zraggenmadang-nake	Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea
nana1257	Nanai	lexibank-northeuralex-nanai	Eurasia	Tungusic
nanc1254	Nanchang	lexibank-beidasinitic-Nanchang	Eurasia	Sino-Tibetan
naru1238	Narrungga	ausphonlex_v0-4:Narrungga	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
nede1245	Nedebang	lexibank-robinsonap-nedebang	Papunesia	Timor-Alor-Pantar
nend1239	Nend	lexibank-zraggenmadang-nend	Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea
nene1249	Tundranenets	lexibank-northeuralex-tundranenets	Eurasia	Uralic
ngaa1240	Ngaanyatjarra	ausphonlex_v0-4:Ngaanyatjarra	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
ngad1258	Ngadjunmaya	ausphonlex_v0-4:Ngadjunmaya	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
ngal1292	Dalabon	ausphonlex_v0-4:Dalabon	Australia	Gunwinyguan
ngal1293	Ngalakgan	ausphonlex_v0-4:Ngalakgan	Australia	Gunwinyguan
ngam1284	Ngamini	ausphonlex_v0-4:Ngamini	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
ngan1291	Nganasan	lexibank-northeuralex-nganasan	Eurasia	Uralic
ngan1295	Ngandi	ausphonlex_v0-4:Ngandi	Australia	Gunwinyguan
east2376	Ngarinyman	ausphonlex_v0-4:Ngarinyman	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
ngar1284	Ngarinyin	ausphonlex_v0-4:Ngarinyin	Australia	Worrorran
ngar1287	Ngarluma	ausphonlex_v0-4:Ngarluma	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
ngar1296	Ngarla	ausphonlex_v0-4:Ngarla	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
ngaw1240	Ngawun	ausphonlex_v0-4:Ngawun	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
nhan1238	Nhanda	ausphonlex_v0-4:Nhanda	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
nhir1234	Nhirrpi	ausphonlex_v0-4:Nhirrpi	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
nija1241	Niyaparli	ausphonlex_v0-4:Niyaparli	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
nobo1238	Nobonob	lexibank-zraggenmadang-nobonob	Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea
nort2641	Northernkurdish	lexibank-northeuralex-northernkurdish	Eurasia	Indo-European
nort2646	Northernpashto	lexibank-northeuralex-northernpashto	Eurasia	Indo-European
nort2671	Northernsami	lexibank-northeuralex-northernsami	Eurasia	Uralic
nort2690	Northernuzbek	lexibank-northeuralex-northernuzbek	Eurasia	Turkic
nort2697	Northazerbaijani	lexibank-northeuralex-northazerbaijani	Eurasia	Turkic
nort2724	Luobenzhuo	lexibank-allenbai-Luobenzhuo	Eurasia	Sino-Tibetan
nort2745	Northernyukaghir	lexibank-northeuralex-northernyukaghir	Eurasia	Yukaghir
nort2972	Emberadarien	lexibank-hubercolumbian-emberadarien	Americas	Chocoan
norw1258	Norwegianbokmal	lexibank-northeuralex-norwegianbokmal	Eurasia	Indo-European
nucl1235	Armenian	lexibank-northeuralex-armenian	Eurasia	Indo-European
nucl1301	Turkish	lexibank-northeuralex-turkish	Eurasia	Turkic
nucl1302	Georgian	lexibank-northeuralex-georgian	Eurasia	Kartvelian
nucl1305	Kannada	lexibank-northeuralex-kannada	Eurasia	Dravidian
nucl1643	Japanese	lexibank-northeuralex-japanese	Eurasia	Japonic

nucl1660	Bora	lexibank-hubercolumbian-bora	Americas	Boran
nugu1241	Nukunu	ausphonlex_v0-4:Nukunu	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
nuka1242	Nukak	lexibank-hubercolumbian-nukak	Americas	Kakua-Nukak
nung1290	Wubuy	ausphonlex_v0-4:Wubuy	Australia	Gunwinyguan
nung1291	Nungali	ausphonlex_v0-4:Nungali	Australia	Mirndi
nupo1240	Witotonipode	lexibank-hubercolumbian-witotonipode	Americas	Huitotoan
nyam1271	Nyamal	ausphonlex_v0-4:Nyamal	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
nyan1301	Nyangumarta	ausphonlex_v0-4:Nyangumarta	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
nyaw1247	Nyawaygi	ausphonlex_v0-4:Nyawaygi	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
nyig1240	Nyikina	ausphonlex_v0-4:Nyikina	Australia	Nyulnyulan
ocai1244	Ocaina	lexibank-hubercolumbian-ocaina	Americas	Huitotoan
ogea1238	Ogea	lexibank-zraggenmadang-ogea	Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea
orej1242	Orejon	lexibank-hubercolumbian-orejon	Americas	Tucanoan
osse1243	Ossetian	lexibank-northeuralex-ossetian	Eurasia	Indo-European
ouji1238	Wenzhou	lexibank-beidasinitic-Wenzhou	Eurasia	Sino-Tibetan
oyka1239	Oykangand	ausphonlex_v0-4:Oykangand	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
paez1247	Paez	lexibank-hubercolumbian-paez	Americas	Páez
paka1251	Bakanh	ausphonlex_v0-4:Bakanh	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
pall1244	Pal	lexibank-zraggenmadang-pal	Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea
pamo1253	Pamosu	lexibank-zraggenmadang-pamosu	Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea
pamo1254	Bara	lexibank-hubercolumbian-bara	Americas	Tucanoan
pani1258	Panim	lexibank-zraggenmadang-panim	Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea
pany1241	Panyjima	ausphonlex_v0-4:Panyjima	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
payn1244	Paynamar	lexibank-zraggenmadang-paynamar	Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea
peri1265	Giacone	lexibank-hubercolumbian-giacone	Americas	Arawakan
peri1265	Tariano	lexibank-hubercolumbian-tariano	Americas	Arawakan
piap1246	Piapoco	lexibank-hubercolumbian-piapoco	Americas	Arawakan
pila1246	Maia-Pila	lexibank-zraggenmadang-maia-pila	Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea
pint1250	Pintupi	ausphonlex_v0-4:Pintupi	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
pira1254	Piratapuyo	lexibank-hubercolumbian-piratapuyo	Americas	Tucanoan
pitj1243	Ngalia	ausphonlex_v0-4:Ngalia	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
pitt1247	Pitta Pitta	ausphonlex_v0-4:Pitta Pitta	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
play1240	Playero	lexibank-hubercolumbian-playero	Americas	Guahiboan
poli1260	Polish	lexibank-northeuralex-polish	Eurasia	Indo-European
port1283	Portuguese	lexibank-northeuralex-portuguese	Eurasia	Indo-European
pudi1238	Putjarra	ausphonlex_v0-4:Putjarra	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
puin1248	Puinave	lexibank-hubercolumbian-puinave	Americas	Puinave
pula1267	Pulabu	lexibank-zraggenmadang-pulabu	Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea
pung1239	Patjtjamalh	ausphonlex_v0-4:Patjtjamalh	Australia	Wadjiginy
qili1234	Qiliqiao	lexibank-allenbai-Qiliqiao	Eurasia	Sino-Tibetan

rapt1240	Rapting	lexibank-zraggenmadang-rapting	Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea
remb1249	Rembarrnga	ausphonlex_v0-4:Rembarrnga	Australia	Gunwinyguan
remp1241	Rempi	lexibank-zraggenmadang-rempi	Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea
raera1240	Rerau	lexibank-zraggenmadang-rerau	Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea
resi1247	Resigaro	lexibank-hubercolumbian-resigaro	Americas	Arawakan
rita1239	Ritharrngu	ausphonlex_v0-4:Ritharrngu	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
roma1327	Romanian	lexibank-northeuralex-romanian	Eurasia	Indo-European
russ1263	Russian	lexibank-northeuralex-russian	Eurasia	Indo-European
saep1240	Saep	lexibank-zraggenmadang-saep	Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea
sali1298	Saliba	lexibank-hubercolumbian-saliba	Americas	Jodi-Saliban
samm1244	Sam	lexibank-zraggenmadang-sam	Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea
samo1306	Samosa	lexibank-zraggenmadang-samosa	Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea
saru1243	Saruga	lexibank-zraggenmadang-saruga	Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea
saus1246	Sausi	lexibank-zraggenmadang-sausi	Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea
sawi1256	Sawila	lexibank-robinsonap-sawila	Papunesia	Timor-Alor-Pantar
seco1241	Secoya	lexibank-hubercolumbian-secoya	Americas	Tucanoan
selk1253	Northernselekup	lexibank-northeuralex-northernselekup	Eurasia	Uralic
shen1252	Shenyang	lexibank-beidasinitic-Shenyang	Eurasia	Sino-Tibetan
siha1245	Sihan	lexibank-zraggenmadang-sihan	Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea
sile1255	Sileibi	lexibank-zraggenmadang-sileibi	Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea
silo1240	Silopi	lexibank-zraggenmadang-silopi	Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea
sins1241	Sinsauru	lexibank-zraggenmadang-sinsauru	Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea
sion1247	Siona	lexibank-hubercolumbian-siona	Americas	Tucanoan
siri1274	Siriano	lexibank-hubercolumbian-siriano	Americas	Tucanoan
siro1249	Siroi	lexibank-zraggenmadang-siroi	Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea
skol1241	Skoltsami	lexibank-northeuralex-skoltsami	Eurasia	Uralic
slov1268	Slovene	lexibank-northeuralex-slovene	Eurasia	Indo-European
slov1269	Slovak	lexibank-northeuralex-slovak	Eurasia	Indo-European
sopp1247	Sop	lexibank-zraggenmadang-sop	Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea
sout2674	Southern sami	lexibank-northeuralex-southern sami	Eurasia	Uralic
sout2750	Southern yukaghir	lexibank-northeuralex-southern yukaghir	Eurasia	Yukaghir
stan1288	Spanish	lexibank-northeuralex-spanish	Eurasia	Indo-European
stan1289	Catalan	lexibank-northeuralex-catalan	Eurasia	Indo-European
stan1290	French	lexibank-northeuralex-french	Eurasia	Indo-European
stan1293	English	lexibank-northeuralex-english	Eurasia	Indo-European
stan1295	German	lexibank-northeuralex-german	Eurasia	Indo-European
stan1318	Standard arabic	lexibank-northeuralex-standard arabic	Eurasia	Afro-Asiatic
suma1270	Sumau	lexibank-zraggenmadang-sumau	Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea
suzh1234	Suzhou	lexibank-beidasinitic-Suzhou	Eurasia	Sino-Tibetan
swed1254	Swedish	lexibank-northeuralex-swedish	Eurasia	Indo-European

tami1289	Tamil	lexibank-northeastalex-tamil	Eurasia	Dravidian
tani1257	Tanimuca	lexibank-hubercolumbian-tanimuca	Americas	Tucanoan
tata1255	Tatar	lexibank-northeastalex-tatar	Eurasia	Turkic
tatu1247	Tatuyo	lexibank-hubercolumbian-tatuyo	Americas	Tucanoan
tauy1241	Tauya	lexibank-zraggenmadang-tauya	Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea
teiw1235	Teiwa	lexibank-robinsonap-teiwa	Papunesia	Timor-Alor-Pantar
telu1262	Telugu	lexibank-northeastalex-telugu	Eurasia	Dravidian
tiwi1244	Tiwi	ausphonlex_v0-4:Tiwi	Australia	Tiwi
toto1306	Totoro	lexibank-hubercolumbian-totoro	Americas	Barbacoan
tuca1252	Tucano	lexibank-hubercolumbian-tucano	Americas	Tucanoan
tuyu1244	Tuyuca	lexibank-hubercolumbian-tuyuca	Americas	Tucanoan
tyan1235	Thaynakwithi	ausphonlex_v0-4:Thaynakwithi	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
udmu1245	Udmurt	lexibank-northeastalex-udmurt	Eurasia	Uralic
ukra1253	Ukrainian	lexibank-northeastalex-ukrainian	Eurasia	Indo-European
ukur1240	Ukuriguma	lexibank-zraggenmadang-ukuriguma	Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea
ulku1238	Olkol	ausphonlex_v0-4:Olkol	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
umpi1239	Umpila	ausphonlex_v0-4:Umpila	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
ungg1243	Unggumi	ausphonlex_v0-4:Unggumi	Australia	Worrorran
urig1240	Urigina	lexibank-zraggenmadang-urigina	Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea
urni1239	Urningangg	ausphonlex_v0-4:Urningangg	Australia	Giimbiyu
usan1239	Usan	lexibank-zraggenmadang-usan	Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea
utar1238	Utarmbung	lexibank-zraggenmadang-utarmbung	Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea
utuu1240	Utu	lexibank-zraggenmadang-utu	Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea
uyaa1238	Uya	lexibank-zraggenmadang-uya	Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea
veps1250	Veps	lexibank-northeastalex-veps	Eurasia	Uralic
wada1263	Wadaginam	lexibank-zraggenmadang-wadaginam	Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea
waga1260	Western Wakaya	ausphonlex_v0-4:Western Wakaya	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
wage1238	Wagiman	ausphonlex_v0-4:Wagiman	Australia	Wageman
wagi1249	Wagi	lexibank-zraggenmadang-wagi	Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea
waja1257	Watjarri	ausphonlex_v0-4:Watjarri	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
walm1241	Walmajarri	ausphonlex_v0-4:Walmajarri	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
wama1247	Wamas	lexibank-zraggenmadang-wamas	Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea
nucl1328	Wambaya	ausphonlex_v0-4:Wambaya	Australia	Mirndi
wana1269	Wanambre	lexibank-zraggenmadang-wanambre	Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea
wand1263	Warndarrang	ausphonlex_v0-4:Warndarrang	Australia	Mangarrayi-Maran
wang1288	Wangkajunga	ausphonlex_v0-4:Wangkajunga	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
wang1291	Ngiyambaa	ausphonlex_v0-4:Ngiyambaa	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
wanm1242	Warnman	ausphonlex_v0-4:Warnman	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
wany1244	Wanyjirra	ausphonlex_v0-4:Wanyjirra	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
wany1247	Waanyi	ausphonlex_v0-4:Waanyi	Australia	Garrwan

ward1246	Wardaman	ausphonlex_v0-4:Wardaman	Australia	Yangmanic
wari1262	Wariyangga	ausphonlex_v0-4:Wariyangga	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
warl1254	Warlpiri	ausphonlex_v0-4:Warlpiri	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
warl1255	Warlmanpa	ausphonlex_v0-4:Warlmanpa	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
warl1256	Warluwarra	ausphonlex_v0-4:Warluwarra	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
warr1255	Warrgamay	ausphonlex_v0-4:Warrgamay	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
wask1241	Waskia	lexibank-zraggenmadang-waskia	Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea
wayi1238	Wayilwan	ausphonlex_v0-4:Wayilwan	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
wayu1243	Wayuu	lexibank-hubercolumbian-wayuu	Americas	Arawakan
wels1247	Welsh	lexibank-northeuralex-welsh	Eurasia	Indo-European
wemb1241	Wemba Wemba	ausphonlex_v0-4:Wemba Wemba	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
wers1238	Wersing	lexibank-robinsonap-wersing	Papunesia	Timor-Alor-Pantar
west2369	Westernfarsi	lexibank-northeuralex-westernfarsi	Eurasia	Indo-European
west2392	Hillmari	lexibank-northeuralex-hillmari	Eurasia	Uralic
west2437	Ngardily	ausphonlex_v0-4:Ngardily	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
west2441	Western Arrernte	ausphonlex_v0-4:Western Arrernte	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
wikm1247	Wik Mungkan	ausphonlex_v0-4:Wik Mungkan	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
wikn1246	Kugu Nganhcara	ausphonlex_v0-4:Kugu Nganhcara	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
wira1262	Wiradjuri	ausphonlex_v0-4:Wiradjuri	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
wira1265	Wirangu	ausphonlex_v0-4:Wirangu	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
wong1246	Wangkumara	ausphonlex_v0-4:Wangkumara	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
woro1258	Worrorra	ausphonlex_v0-4:Worrorra	Australia	Worrorran
wotj1234	Wotjobaluk	ausphonlex_v0-4:Wotjobaluk	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
woun1238	Wounaan	lexibank-hubercolumbian-wounaan	Americas	Chocoan
wulg1239	Wulguru	ausphonlex_v0-4:Wulguru	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
xiam1236	Xiamen	lexibank-beidasinitic-Xiamen	Eurasia	Sino-Tibetan
xian1250	Xiangyun	lexibank-allenbai-Xiangyun	Eurasia	Sino-Tibetan
xian1253	Xi An	lexibank-beidasinitic-Xi_an	Eurasia	Sino-Tibetan
yabe1255	Yaben	lexibank-zraggenmadang-yaben	Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea
yabo1240	Yabong	lexibank-zraggenmadang-yabong	Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea
yadh1237	Yadhaykenu	ausphonlex_v0-4:Yadhaykenu	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
yaku1245	Sakha	lexibank-northeuralex-sakha	Eurasia	Turkic
yala1262	Yalarnnga	ausphonlex_v0-4:Yalarnnga	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
yand1253	Yandruwandha	ausphonlex_v0-4:Yandruwandha	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
yang1298	Yangulam	lexibank-zraggenmadang-yangulam	Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea
yang1306	Yangzhou	lexibank-beidasinitic-Yangzhou	Eurasia	Sino-Tibetan
yang1307	Yangjiang	lexibank-beidasinitic-Yangjiang	Eurasia	Sino-Tibetan
yann1237	Nhangu	ausphonlex_v0-4:Nhangu	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
yany1243	Yanyuwa	ausphonlex_v0-4:Yanyuwa	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
yara1250	Yarawata	lexibank-zraggenmadang-yarawata	Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea

yarl1238	Yarluyandi	ausphonlex_v0-4:Yarluyandi	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
yawi1239	Yawijibaya	ausphonlex_v0-4:Yawijibaya	Australia	Worrorran
yayg1236	Yaygir	ausphonlex_v0-4:Yaygir	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
yidi1250	Yidiny	ausphonlex_v0-4:Yidiny	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
yind1247	Yindjibarndi	ausphonlex_v0-4:Yindjibarndi	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
ying1247	Yingkarta	ausphonlex_v0-4:Yingkarta	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
yinh1234	Yinhawangka	ausphonlex_v0-4:Yinhawangka	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
yoid1240	Yoidik	lexibank-zraggenmadang-yoidik	Papunesia	NuclearTransNewGuinea
yort1237	Yorta Yorta	ausphonlex_v0-4:Yorta Yorta	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
yucu1253	Yucuna	lexibank-hubercolumbian-yucuna	Americas	Arawakan
yuet1238	Meixian	lexibank-beidasinitic-Meixian	Eurasia	Sino-Tibetan
yukp1241	Yukpa	lexibank-hubercolumbian-yukpa	Americas	Cariban
yulp1239	Yulparija	ausphonlex_v0-4:Yulparija	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
yunl1238	Yunlong	lexibank-allenbai-Yunlong	Eurasia	Sino-Tibetan
yuru1263	Yuruti	lexibank-hubercolumbian-yuruti	Americas	Tucanoan
yuwa1242	Yuwaalaraay	ausphonlex_v0-4:Yuwaalaraay	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
yuwa1243	Yuwaliyaay	ausphonlex_v0-4:Yuwaliyaay	Australia	Pama-Nyungan
zhou1234	Zhoucheng	lexibank-allenbai-Zhoucheng	Eurasia	Sino-Tibetan